

THE SYSTEM OF FORMING THE NATIONAL WORLD VIEW OF FUTURE TEACHERS.

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Annotation: In this thesis, future teachers will be taught to create professional creativity and skills, to approach the current educational process through new pedagogical projects, the aspects of pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills will be highlighted, and the organization of the teaching process will be their world. issues such as development of vision, relations between teacher and student, speech culture, formation of pedagogical technique skills are explained.

Key words: Education, Future teacher, World view, Formation of world view, Pedagogue with a broad world view, Pedagogical skill.

Main part: In the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the twenty-ninth anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "To fully realize the talents and abilities of our children, noble aspirations, to increase their social activity, to occupy a worthy place in life creating all the opportunities for children will remain our main goal from now on... For this purpose, we are introducing the science of "Education" for the first time in general education schools within the framework of the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education", the people emphasized. He set great tasks for the employees of the Ministry of Education and the teachers of the school.

So, what is education? What qualities should a future educator have? Let's express our thoughts in this regard.

Education is important in the development of a person's intelligence, knowledge, will and faith, qualities of maturity. As an unquenchable torch, it effortlessly brings one to the kingdom of bliss.

At the same time, education shows the way to reach bright heights under any circumstances, it sharpens a person's mind and thoughts like a sword, and gives spiritual nourishment to every person, bringing them to the world of culture and

enlightenment. Prevents bad people and bad deeds. Serves to be good manners and polite. As a result, people will be dear and respected everywhere. Education is the tool that sets a person's life on the right path. That is why great people who have achieved high qualities, greatness and dreams through education are appreciated among the people. Education perfects qualities of social importance, such as knowing good and bad, knowing the difference between honest and bad, understanding the virtues of friendship and relatives, understanding laws and regulations, and knowing one's rights.

In our country, a child receives education from parents in the family, and from a teacher-coach at school. Here, it is necessary to highlight the role of teachers in education. In the organization of educational work, it is important for the teacher to develop prospective plans and to give importance to the content, terms of each event, responsible performers and the level of effectiveness of the planned activities. In this regard, the future teacher should have the experience of analyzing educational processes, using different methods, actively thinking consciously, mobilizing knowledge, and independently implementing all the work processes he performs. It is necessary to have pedagogical skills.

"Pedagogical skill" defines the main goal of forming professional skills, creativity, skills of future pedagogues, formation of communication culture, pedagogic technique skills, teaching and educational skills. In the process of studying "pedagogical skill", students are taught to independently master pedagogical observation, creativity, advanced pedagogical experiences. In the process of studying, teaching, educating, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of the skills of clear distribution of attention, ability to manage knowledge, skills, mental states, and independent assimilation of the culture of pedagogical techniques. Thus, a person's spiritual growth, life experience, knowledge, behavior, manners, morals, professional skills, his meaningfulness and, finally, how much he improves it, are different.

When it comes to the scientific worldview, first of all, students, young people, should understand the need to form a scientific worldview, because there are religious, fantastic, mythological, atheistic and other non-scientific worldviews that are contrary to it, to think about it correctly. They need to learn. Worldview is a very complex dialectical process that is formed only by knowing the world. Knowledge is realized through the works given by different sciences about different aspects of the world. Therefore, people without knowledge do not have a scientific outlook on

the world. Worldview consists of a set of scientific, philosophical, political, legal, ethical, aesthetic, religious ideas of people about the world and its changes and development. Worldview determines the direction of activity and attitude to reality of some people, social group, class or society as a whole. When scientific knowledge is included in the worldview, it serves the purpose of taking a direct practical approach to the surrounding social and natural existence of a person or group.

Conclusion: This system provides education to form students' national outlook and increase its value. In this system, students can study national spirituality, history, culture and other national experiences and increase their identity. This system helps students to strengthen their national identity by appreciating and respecting their national values.

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